

4Q209 frg. 4 + PAM 43.666 frg. 41 (IAA Pl. 88, frg. 35)

Eibert Tigchelaar, KU Leuven

April 5, 2022

PAM 43.666 frg. 41, one of the many hundreds of hitherto unidentified fragments on the Museum plates published in DJD 33, can be identified as a 4Q209 (4QEnastr^b) fragment, which should be joined to 4Q209 frg. 4 lines 3-4 (published in Tigchelaar and García Martínez, DJD 36, 141-42 and Drawnel, 151-52). In the image below, I have separated the two pieces of PAM 43.666 frg. 41 (the left one with the letters **בִּי**; the right with the remainder) which were not perfectly aligned on the photographs, as can be seen from the absence of the downstroke of *bet*.

See the following transcription with 4Q209 frg. 4 lines 3-4 in blue, PAM 43.666 frg. 41 in red, and reconstructed text in black (following the reconstruction of Drawnel, 152).

[ובלילא תלתה ועשרין בה כס] **ה שביעין ארבעה** [ו] **פִּלְגֹּב וּבְצִיר** [מנהורה שביעין ארבעה ופִּלְגֹּב] 3
[ובאדין נפק ואניר בשאר] **ל** [י] **ל** [י] **א** [] **דָּן שְׁבִיעִי** [ן תריין ו] **פִּלְגֹּב** [וקוי ביממא דן שביעין חמשה] 4

The join of the newly identified fragment confirms the textual reconstruction based on the pattern of computation, and hence does not add anything of substance to scholarship.

Images of PAM 43.666 frg. 41

DJD 33, Pl. VII

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285445> (PAM 43.666)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-501458> (IAA Pl. 88, frg. 35 colour)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-501459> (IAA Pl. 88, frg. 35 infrared)

References

- DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, eds., *Qumran Cave 4. XXIII: Unidentified Fragments. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)
- DJD 36 *Qumran Cave 4. XXVI Cryptic Texts and Miscellanea, Part 1* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2000)
- Drawnel Henryk Drawnel, *The Aramaic Astronomical Book (4Q208-4Q211) from Qumran: Text, Translation, and Commentary* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum